

Continued Folic Acid Supplementation Throughout Pregnancy, May Cause Colorectal Cancer In The Future

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Abstract

Folic acid supplementation during early pregnancy protects from spina bifida and avoids either a spontaneous miscarriage or a severe developmental defect causing early postnatal death, associated with spina bifida, microcephaly or anencephaly. However, Based on epidemiological data in both the U.S. and Canada showed an increase in the incidence of colorectal cancer beginning when folic acid fortification in wheat-based products became mandatory and continued folic acid supplementation throughout pregnancy can increase the risk of colorectal cancer in the future.

Keywords:

Pregnancy, Folic Acid Supplementation, Colorectal Cancer, Spina Bifida

Introduction & Methods

Folate is intimately involved in the complex biological pathways that maintain S-adenosylmethionine, the universal methyl donor, and it also feeds into the synthesis of purine and thymidine units in DNA and RNA. The one-carbon metabolic pathway (one-carbon = the methyl group), mediated by folate, plays a vital role in hemoglobin synthesis and DNA synthesis, repair and methylation.¹ For these reasons, it is generally believed that a diet high in folate should be protective against cancer, which arises from DNA mutations. In particular, there is a fairly compelling case for folate being protective against colorectal cancer (CRC).² Folate may also be protective against breast cancer and uterine cancer.³

Given the above, one would expect that folic acid supplementation would decrease the incidence of colorectal cancer. Ironically, epidemiological data in both the U.S. and Canada showed an increase in the incidence of colorectal cancer beginning when folic acid fortification in wheat-based products became mandatory.⁴ These authors wrote in the abstract: “We therefore hypothesize that the institution of folic acid fortification may have been wholly or partly responsible for the observed increase in CRC rates in the mid-1990s.”

A study by Troen and others confirmed that unmodified and therefore inactive folic acid was present in the blood among 78 percent of one hundred five post-menopausal women.⁵ Over half of them were taking a folic acid supplement daily. The study found that the ability of natural killer cells to destroy neoplastic (potentially cancerous) cells was reduced when folic acid levels were elevated. What is probably happening is that the inactive folic acid is binding to the folate receptors and preventing access by the methyltetrahydrofolate. This gives a hint as to how excess folic acid might increase risk to cancer by getting in the way.

(Methyltetrahydro) folate protects from cancer by preventing DNA mutations, which can turn off cancer-protective genes and cause cells to start proliferating uncontrollably. However, folate also *fuels* proliferation, because it is necessary for the synthesis of certain DNA nucleotides. Once you have a cancer growing, folate will encourage the cancer to grow bigger. Part of the chemotherapy program used to treat cancer involves anti-folate drugs: drugs that interfere with folate signaling.^{6,7} While these drugs prevent growth of the existing tumor, they also encourage further DNA mutations, which could lead to metastasis from the tumor, and it will also cause an increased risk of new cancers.

A randomized placebo-controlled trial intended to test the potential benefit of folic acid supplements in colon cancer showed instead that people with a history of colorectal adenomas had an increased risk of a more severe recurrence if they took 1 mg folic acid per day.⁸ Another paper showed that oral folic acid supplements increase the risk of prostate cancer. Meanwhile, anti-folate chemotherapy treatments are being widely administered to actively reduce the bioavailability of folate, which has been shown to fuel cancer growth, for both breast cancer and non-Hodgkin's lymphoma.^{6,7}

On top of the folic acid that is present as fortification of flour, bread and pasta, about 30-40 percent of North Americans also take folic acid supplements. And supplements are usually recommended during pregnancy, with a disregard for potential toxicity. There is an increasing concern that the widespread practice of folic acid fortification is leading to an over-consumption

of folic acid. A study of four healthy adult volunteers involved administering folic-acid-enriched bread and then analyzing for the presence of synthetic unmodified folic acid in the blood. Serum folic acid was found in all subjects at all doses tested.⁹

In an experiment to test the effects of folic acid on mammary tumors in female Sprague-Dawley rats, rats with tumors were randomized to receive a diet containing varying amounts of folic acid supplements, for up to twelve weeks, and the growth of their tumors was monitored.¹⁰ Folic acid supplementation at all levels significantly promoted the progression of mammary tumors, with increases in both weight and volume compared to the control diet without any supplement. These authors wrote: “This is a critically important issue because breast cancer patients and survivors in North America are likely exposed to high levels of folic acid owing to folic acid fortification and widespread supplemental use after cancer diagnosis.”

Conclusion

The best way to maintain adequate supplies of folate during pregnancy, is to eat a strictly organic diet that is rich in fresh vegetables, seafood, eggs, and grass-fed beef and liver. Particularly good sources of folate include beef liver, spinach, black-eyed peas, asparagus, Brussels sprouts, avocado, broccoli, mustard greens, green peas and kidney beans. After the first stage of pregnancy the supplementation of folic acid should be halted and the increase in consumption of natural folate should be prescribed.

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